

Synthesis of 4-Aryl-3-Mercaptobenzyl-5-Phenylimino-1,2,4-Thiadiazolines

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Interaction of S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and 1-aryl-S-benzylisothiocarbamides and parent S-benzylisothiocarbamide has been found to afford 4-aryl-3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolines and 3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazoline respectively. Chemistry and IR spectra of these compounds have been studied.

USING S-Chloro-N-arylthiocarbamoyl chloride and appropriate thiocarbamides, synthesis of certain 4 and 5 substituted-3-thio-1, 2, 4-dithiazolidines, 5-arylimino-3-thio-1, 2, 4-dithiazolidines and their 3-mercaptobenzyl derivatives has been carried out and reported in earlier communications^{1,2}.

The following account relates to the reaction in cold benzene medium of the above thiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzylisothiocarbamides leading to the formation of the corresponding 4 and 5 substituted-3-mercaptobenzyl-1, 2, 4-thiadiazolines (I). The other likely product of the reaction viz. II is not formed. The formation of I is found to have been preceded by an unstable intermediate having most probably, the structure III.

Where (a) R = *p*-tolyl
(b) R = phenyl
(c) R = *p*-chlorophenyl
(d) R = hydrogen
and Bz = benzyl

For example, the reaction of S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl-*p*-tolylisothiocarbamide in well cooled benzene medium afforded a compound C₂₂H₂₀N₃S₂Cl, HCl (IIIa), which was acidic and was unstable to moisture. It was desulphurisable when boiled with alkali plumbite solution. On heating under reflux with benzene, it dissolved with evolution of hydrogen chloride, and on cooling deposited fine, shining colourless needles C₂₂H₁₉N₃S₂, m. p. 110°. It was found nondesulphurisable when boiled with alkali plumbite solution. On heating, it decomposed and smell of benzylmercaptan and phenylisothiocyanate were apparent. It afforded a picrate.

On treatment with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration it formed a new

product C₂₂H₂₁N₃S₂, (m.p. 96°) which was found desulphurisable. On oxidation with iodine it re-formed the original compound, m.p. 110°. On prolonged treatment with concentrated solution of alcoholic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide it afforded 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide in small quantities along with benzyl mercaptan.

Earlier experiments³ on such ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide reduction of certain 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines have shown that the reaction leads to ring opening by the breaking of N-S bond. In the present case such a course of reaction could lead to two different dithiobiuret derivatives IVa and Va depending on whether Ia or IIa respectively, represented the structure of the compound (m.p. 110°).

where Bz = benzyl and pT = *p*-tolyl

Since only IVa on further reduction can give rise to 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide, which has been obtained in small quantities in this reaction (*vide supra*), it was evident that Ia must represent the structure of the original compound from which it was derived.

The structure IVa for the reduction product was also supported on the basis of the presence of C=S, -NH, C=N and C-S.Bz stretching bands in its IR spectrum. Further the compound Va has been synthesised independently⁴ and is found different from the compound IVa.

The structure of the compound (C₂₂H₁₉N₃S₂, m. p. 110°) is therefore, established as 3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-4-*p*-tolyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (Ia). It is also supported by its IR spectrum which showed the presence of C=N, C-S.Bz, ring C-N bands. Following scheme can therefore be written for the formation of Ia-d, where different aryl groups are present in the S-benzyl arylisothiocarbamides.

- where (a) R=*p*-tolyl
 (b) R=phenyl
 (c) R=*p*-chlorophenyl
 (d) R=hydrogen
 and Bz=benzyl

The identity of the product Id has been established by its independent synthesis by the oxidation of 4-S-benzyliso-1-phenyl-2-thiobiuret⁵ (VI).

IR spectrum of Id indicated, as expected, the presence of -NH, C=N, C-S.Bz bands further supporting the proposed structure.

Experimental

The S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride was prepared by an earlier known method⁶. The required 1-aryl S-benzylisothiocarbamides⁷ (where aryl=*p*-tolyl, phenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl) and the parent S-benzylisothiocarbamide⁸ were prepared by the reaction of benzyl chloride with appropriate thiocarbamides followed by basification with aqueous ammonia.

1. Interaction of S-Chloro-N phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides in cold benzene medium: Formation of 4-aryl-3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolines (I) through III.

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=*p*-tolyl) are as follows.

When to a well cooled solution of *p*-tolyl S-benzylisothiocarbamide in benzene (24 g in 100 ml) was added gradually a cold solution of S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g in 50 ml benzene) and the mixture maintained at 5° by cooling in a freezing mixture, a reaction with evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. After standing for several hours a solid separated which was filtered out quickly and washed several times with benzene followed by petroleum ether when a product C₂₂H₂₀N₃S₂Cl.HCl, m.p. 127°d (Found: N, 9.00; S, 13.46; C₂₂N₂₀N₃S₂Cl.HCl requires; N, 9.09; S, 13.86%) was obtained. It was acidic in nature (a hydrochloride), unstable to moisture and was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkali plumbite solution. On heating, it decomposed and smell of benzyl mercaptan was perceptible. This rather unstable compound on heating with benzene under reflux for two hours dissolved with evolution of hydrogen chloride. The resultant solution on cooling deposited fine, shining, colourless needles (20 g); recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 110° (Found: C, 67.52; H, 4.76; N, 10.60; S, 16.47; C₂₂H₁₉N₃S₂ requires; C, 67.87; H, 4.89; N, 10.80; S, 16.45%).

The product was found non-desulphurisable on boiling with alkali plumbite solution but afforded a yellow precipitate of lead mercaptide. On heating in dry test tube, it decomposed and odours of benzyl mercaptan and phenyl isothiocyanate were apparent. It afforded a picrate, crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 162° (Found: N, 12.97; C₂₂H₁₉N₃S₂.C₆H₃N₃O₇ requires; N, 13.59%).

The IR spectrum of this picrate indicated the presence of C-S.Bz^{10a}, C=N^{10b}, and OH^{10c} stretching bands at 1260, 1655 and 3380 cm⁻¹ respectively

The compound (2 g) on reaction for several hours with cold ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration afforded a product (1 g). On boiling with water a small part of it was found to dissolve and crystallise out and the water insoluble residue left behind on crystallisation from aqueous ethanol afforded a solid m.p. 96° (Found: C, 67.20; H, 5.60; N, 10.32; S, 16.47. C₂₂H₂₁N₃S₂ requires C, 67.51; H, 5.37; N, 10.74; S, 16.37%). This compound was found desulphurisable with hot alkali plumbite solution, which was suggestive of a thiocarbamidic grouping in its structure. The crystals that had separated (m.p. 198°) from the aqueous extract were identified as a dimorphous form of the product with m.p. 96° through their superimposable IR spectrum.

On prolonged reaction at room temperature of this product (m. p. 96°) with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide of strong concentration followed by acidification afforded benzyl mercaptan and another product

(0.2g). The latter on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 141°. (Found : N, 11.43. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2S$ requires ; N, 11.57%). It was identified as 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolyl thiocarbamide through its m.p. and undepressed m.m.p. with an authentic sample⁹.

The IR spectrum of Ia indicated the presence of C-S.Bz^{10a}, C=N^{10b} stretching bands at 1250 and 1650 cm^{-1} respectively, further confirming its structure.

Oxidation of the product (m.p. 96°)

On treating an aqueous ethanolic solution of the m.p. compound (1 g in 10 ml) with an excess of aqueous iodine and basifying, a solid was precipitated; crystallised from benzene, m.p. 110°. This was found identical with the product Ia described above through its m.p. and undepressed m.m.p.

On the basis of the above facts the compound of m.p. 96° obtained on reaction of the original product (Ia m.p. 110°) with ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide, has been assigned the structure 4-S-benzyliso-1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolyl-2-thiobiuret (IVa).

This structure is further supported by its IR spectrum in which presence of C-S.Bz^{10a}, C=S^{10a} and C=N^{10b} at 1440, 1220 and 1600 cm^{-1} respectively has been noticed.

Va has been synthesised as follows and is found different from the above described compound (IVa).

1. Synthesis of Va

A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (1.5 ml) and S-benzyl *p*-tolylisothiocarbamide (2.6 g) in acetone was allowed to stand for a few hours. On evaporation of acetone and heating the residue with a little ethanol, a solid (3 g), m.p. 80°, was obtained. On crystallisation from ethanol, m.p. 84° (Found : N, 10.30 ; S, 16.23. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$ requires ; N, 10.37 ; S, 16.37%). This was 4-S-benzyliso-1-phenyl-5-*p*-tolyl-2-thiobiuret¹¹ (Va). It was found through its m.p. and depressed m.m.p. different from the above described product obtained by the ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide reduction of Ia.

2. 3-Mercaptobenzyl - 4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (Ib)

S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) and S-benzyl phenylisothiocarbamide (24 g) were allowed to react in cold benzene (100 ml) under conditions analogous to those described above (Expt. 1). An unstable product $C_{21}H_{18}N_3S_2Cl.HCl$ was obtained (Found : N, 9.01 ; S, 14.34 ; $C_{21}H_{18}N_3S_2Cl.HCl$ requires ; N, 9.37 ; S, 14.29%). This was IIIb.

On heating this compound in refluxing benzene for 2 hours, it dissolved with evolution of hydrogen chloride and on cooling deposited fine mass of crystals (20 g). On recrystallisation from benzene, m.p. 132° (Found : N, 10.95 ; S, 16.72 ; $C_{21}H_{17}N_3S_2$ requires ; N, 11.17 ; S, 17.02%). This compound was found non-desulphurisable like the Ia. With picric acid it formed a picrate ; crystals from ethanol, m.p. 144° (Found : N, 14.20. $C_{21}H_{17}N_3S_2 \cdot C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires ; N, 13.93%).

3. 3-Mercaptobenzyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl - 5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (Ic) : The reaction of S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) and S-benzyl *p*-chlorophenylisothiocarbamide (27 g) in cold benzene medium (100 ml) under the conditions described above (*vide* Expt. 1 and 2) afforded a colourless unstable solid (Found : N, 8.35 ; $C_{21}H_{17}N_3S_2Cl_2$, HCl requires N, 8.71%). This was (IIIc). On refluxing in carbon tetrachloride/benzene it dissolved with evolution of hydrogen chloride. Unlike other experiments, cooling the solution did not deposit a solid. However, on addition of petroleum ether (40°-60°) a solid (10 g) precipitated which crystallised from benzene petroleum-ether mixture, m. p. 86° (Found : N, 10.07 ; S, 15.14 ; $C_{21}H_{16}N_3S_2Cl$ requires ; N, 10.26 ; S, 15.63%). This compound was also not desulphurisable with hot alkali plumbite. It gave a picrate ; crystals from ethanol, m. p. 171° (Found : N, 13.04 ; $C_{21}H_{16}N_3S_2Cl.C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires ; N, 13.16%).

4. 3-Mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (Id) : S-Chloro-N-phenyl thiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) and the parent S-benzylisothiocarbamide (16 g) on reaction and working out as above (*vide* Expt. 1) afforded, as expected, an unstable product (IIIId). As in other similar experiments suspension of this in benzene on heating under reflux for 2 hr. liberated hydrogen chloride and gave a clear solution which on cooling deposited a fine, crystalline, compound (20 g). It could be recrystallised from ethanol and also from benzene, m. p. 154° (on analysis, found : C, 59.80 ; H, 4.74 ; N, 14.29 ; S, 21.06. $C_{15}H_{18}N_3S_2$ requires C, 60.20 ; H, 4.34 ; N, 14.05 ; S, 21.40%). It did not depress the m. p. of an authentic sample of Id prepared as follows by an earlier known procedure¹² which confirms its structure as Id.

It afforded a picrate ; crystals from ethanol, m. p. 174° (Found : N, 15.76 ; $C_{15}H_{18}N_3S_2.C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N, 15.92%).

To a clear solution of 4-S-benzyliso-1-phenyl-2-thiobiuret⁶ (3 g) in aqueous ethanol was added an aq. ethanolic solution of iodine until no further decolourisation of iodine was observed. On addition of aqueous ammonia a solid (2.5 g) was precipitated ; crystals from ethanol, m. p. 154° (Found : N, 14.10 ; $C_{15}H_{18}N_3S_2$ requires ; N, 14.01%).

The structure (Id) was further supported by its IR spectrum in which C=N^{10b}, C-S.Bz^{10a}, C-S-C^{10a} and -NH¹⁰ stretching bands at 1600, 1420, 700, and 3200 cm^{-1} respectively, have been identified.

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References

1. M. G. PARANJE and A. S. MAHAJAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 1138.
2. A. S. MAHAJAN and M. G. PARANJE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 51, 237.
3. C. P. JOSHUA, V. K. VERMA and K. S. SURESH, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, 19, 663.
4. T. B. JOHNSON and M. S. ELMER, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 176.
5. F. KURZER and S. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1064.
6. G. OTTMANN and H. HOOKS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 838.
7. A. E. DIXON and J. HAWTHORNE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 122 and 1908, 93, 684.
8. J. J. DONLEAVY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1004.
9. T. OTTERBACHER and F. C. WHITMORE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1909.
10. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, International Edition, New York and London, 1963, (a) p. 286, (b) p. 321, (c) p. 319.
11. S. N. DIXIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 407.
12. C. P. JOSHUA and V. K. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 988.